

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Resolving the identity of commercially cultivated *Ulva* (Ulvaceae, Chlorophyta) in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa

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Abstract

Species of *Ulva* have a wide range of commercial applications and are increasingly being recognized as promising candidates for integrated aquaculture. In South Africa, *Ulva* has been commercially cultivated in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms since 2002, with more than 2000 tonnes of biomass cultivated per annum in land-based paddle raceways. However, the identity of the species of *Ulva* grown on these farms remains uncertain. We therefore characterized samples of *Ulva* cultivated in five integrated multi-trophic aquaculture farms (IMTA) across a wide geographical range and compared them with foliose *Ulva* specimens from neighboring seashores. The molecular markers employed for this study were the chloroplast-encoded Ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase oxygenase (*rbcl*), the Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) of the nuclear, and the chloroplast elongation factor *tufA*. All currently cultivated specimens of *Ulva* were molecularly resolved as a single species, *U. lacinulata*. The same species has been cultivated for over a decade, although a few specimens of two other species were also present in early South African IMTA systems. The name *Ulva uncialis* is adopted for the *Ulva* "Species A" by Fort et al. (2021), *Molecular Ecology Resources*, 22, 86) significantly extending the distribution range for this species. A comparison with wild *Ulva* on seashores close to the farms resulted in five new distribution records for South Africa (*U. lacinulata*, *U. ohnoi*, *U. australis*, *U. stenophylloides*, and *U. aragoënsis*), the first report of a foliose form of *U. compressa* in the region, and one new distribution record for Namibia (*U. australis*). This study reiterates the need for DNA confirmation, especially when identifying morphologically simple macroalgae with potential commercial applications.

KEYWORDS

Blue bioeconomy, DNA barcoding, foliose *Ulva*, IMTA, integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture

Abbreviations: AIC, Akaike information criterion; BCC, Benguela current commission; BI, Bayesian inference; BOL, Bolus herbarium; I&J, Irvin & Johnson; IMTA, Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture; ITS, Internal transcribed spacer; MCMC, Markov chain Monte Carlo; ML, Maximum likelihood; PCR, Polymerase chain reaction; RAXML, Randomized accelerated maximum likelihood; RaxML-NG, Randomized accelerated maximum likelihood next generation; *rbcl*, Ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase oxygenase; *tufA*, Elongation factor TU.

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INTRODUCTION

Ulva, also known as sea lettuce, is a genus in the Chlorophyta with a wide range of commercial applications and is a promising candidate for integrated aquaculture. The commercial cultivation of *Ulva* in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms began in South Africa in 2002. Free-floating wild populations of *Ulva* were initially collected from sheltered waters (harbors or bays) close to the abalone farms and were integrated into existing aquaculture systems (Bolton et al., 2009; Troell et al., 2006). *Ulva* strains from South Africa undergo somatic growth in culture and, therefore, do not become fertile, which limits the need to control their life histories (Bolton et al., 2009; Troell et al., 2006). A recent study (wrongly) reported that *Ulva* could only be cultivated from spores (Balar & Mantri, 2020), but this is not generally the case in land-based *Ulva* systems. In South Africa, fertility has not been observed in culture, and no bladed *Ulva* grows on the sides of the paddle raceway systems, further evidence of a lack of spore production. It has been known for many years that certain strains of *Ulva* are beneficial for vegetative production in land-based systems. For example, in pioneering studies of land-based *Ulva* cultivation, Ryther (1982) stated: “Dr. Howard Levine (U. Mass.) kindly provided the author with a sample of *Ulva lactuca* from a population which he had never observed to become reproductive or to bear fruiting bodies. In the year since it has been grown in our culture system, it has also remained sterile, in contrast to several other strains of the same species grown under the same conditions” (p. 19).

More than 2000t of *Ulva* are grown per annum in South Africa in large integrated oval paddle raceways (~30m long, 0.5–1 m deep), mostly in abalone effluent (Neveux et al., 2018). The cultivated biomass is mainly used as supplementary feed for the abalone and for the bioremediation of effluent water (Bolton et al., 2013, 2016; Neveux et al., 2018). The bioremediation capacity of *Ulva* allows for partial recirculation of water on the farm, which reduces pumping costs and increases the water temperature in these land-based paddle raceways, which in turn leads to faster abalone growth (Bolton et al., 2009; Nobre et al., 2010).

The main integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa are located over ~1925km of coastline ranging from the cool temperate northern west coast of South Africa (Diamond Coast Aquaculture) to the warm temperate southeast coast (Wild Coast Abalone). The very different ambient seawater temperature regimes at these farms range from 17.9 to 18.6°C (monthly mean temperature) at Wild Coast Abalone in Haga-Haga to 11.3–13.3°C at Diamond Coast Aquaculture Farm in Kleinsee (Smit et al., 2017). It is therefore hypothesized that farms over such a large biogeographic range, encompassing different marine

biogeographical provinces (Anderson et al., 2009) may be expected to grow different species of *Ulva*.

The taxonomy and subsequent identification of species of *Ulva* is difficult due to a substantial discordance between morphological and molecular identification (Tran et al., 2022). As such, species misidentifications in the genus are not uncommon, many species are referred to under different names in different regions of the world, and different species sometimes bear the same name (Fort et al., 2021; Tran et al., 2022). A few major studies have been carried out recently on *Ulva* molecular species determination and barcoding, and there is a growing consensus on matching species names with clades using specific molecular markers (e.g., Fort et al., 2021; Loughnane et al., 2008; O’Kelly et al., 2010). The nomenclature of *Ulva* species, the names given to these molecular clades, has therefore been changing considerably, both from the expansion of molecular investigations and from recent studies that have sequenced various type specimens of *Ulva* (e.g., Hughey et al., 2019, 2022). For instance, the name *U. lactuca* has been misapplied in many studies around the globe, and 65% of all entries of *U. lactuca* in the NCBI database typically represent incorrectly labeled specimens of other species of *Ulva* (Fort et al., 2021; Hughey et al., 2019). Similarly, high-throughput sequencing of the type specimen of *U. rigida* placed it in a separate clade from specimens erroneously identified as the widely distributed *U. rigida*. Instead, the clade containing the lectotype of *U. rigida* and specimens previously misidentified as *U. rotundata* from Portugal and Ireland, which therefore represent the true *U. rigida*, were shown to be confined to European waters (Hughey et al., 2022). The clade containing the previously misidentified specimens of the widely distributed *U. rigida* also contained the lectotype of *U. lacunculata* from its type locality in Lesina, Croatia, along with the type material of *U. armoricana*, *U. laetevirens*, and *U. scandinavica* (Hughey et al., 2022). Since *U. lacunculata* is the oldest validly published name in this clade, it is the correct name that should be applied to the globally distributed species that was previously known as *U. rigida* (Hughey et al., 2022). However, according to Fort et al. (2021), *U. lacunculata* and *U. rigida* are two separate species, and the sequences previously assigned to *U. rigida* are provisionally referred to as *Ulva* sp. A by Fort et al. (2021). Since there are currently no described species that are synonymous with the *Ulva* sp. A specimen in public repositories, the sequences of *Ulva* sp. A will need to be renamed when a suitable valid described species is resolved within this clade (Fort et al., 2021).

Ulva that have been commercially grown in integrated aquaculture farms in South Africa have similarly been given different species names in the literature in the past few years based on morphological identification, and identification is especially difficult when these free-living specimens have no basal portion (Cyrus

et al., 2015; Robertson-Andersson et al., 2008; Shuuluka et al., 2013). The first attempt to confirm the identity of this cultivated *Ulva* used the DNA marker ITS region, together with morphology, to identify samples collected from seashores and from one aquaculture farm, Irvin & Johnson Cape Abalone (Kandjengo, 2002). Based on morpho-anatomical and cytological characters, four species of *Ulva*—*U. rigida*, *U. capensis*, *U. lactuca*, and *U. linza*—were identified from the Irvin & Johnson Cape Abalone Farm. However, all four morphological species were resolved as a single molecular species, considered then as *U. rigida* (sensu Stegenga et al., 1997; Kandjengo, 2002). The molecular data suggested that *U. capensis* and *U. rigida* from South Africa represent a single polymorphic species and included a sample collected from the Irvin & Johnson Cape Abalone farm.

Only a few studies on the taxonomy of *Ulva* have been carried out in South Africa. According to Joska (1992), the name *U. uncialis* was considered synonymous with *U. rigida* on morphological grounds. According to Silva et al. (1996), *U. capensis* should be known as *U. uncialis* because *Phycoseris uncialis* is an older name and was considered synonymous with *U. capensis* by Papenfuss. Since Kützing (1849, p. 475) had already proposed a new species for Drège's material (*P. uncialis*), *U. capensis* must be considered superfluous and hence illegitimate. Following Joska (1992), a comprehensive morphological documentation of seaweeds of the South African west coast was conducted by Stegenga et al. (1997). Within the genus *Enteromorpha* (tubular species), six species were identified, namely, *E. intestinalis*, *E. atroviridis*, *E. linza*, *E. compressa*, *E. prolifera*, and *E. flexuosa* (Stegenga et al., 1997; all these species are now in the genus *Ulva*). In the genus *Ulva* (foliose species), five species were identified, namely, *U. fasciata*, *U. capensis*, *U. rigida*, *U. rhacodes*, and *U. lactuca* (Stegenga et al., 1997).

The uncertainty associated with morphological identification coupled with the growing nomenclatural changes in *Ulva* over the last few years led to the aim of this study, which was to identify the species of *Ulva* grown in the main integrated seaweed-abalone farms in South Africa. Five farms—Diamond Coast Aquaculture, Abagold, Irvin & Johnson (I&J) Cape Abalone, Buffeljags Abalone, and Wild Coast Abalone—that are responsible for the production of a large majority of the cultured *Ulva* in South Africa were sampled. Foliose *Ulva* specimens from nearby rocky shores close to the farms in the Hermanus abalone farming complex in New Harbor and available sequences from a previous study (Kandjengo, 2002) were included in our analyses for comparative purposes. We were specifically interested in determining whether the farmed species were also present in wild marine habitats close to the farms. Specimens of *Ulva* were identified morphologically, and three molecular markers, *rbcl*, ITS rDNA region, and *tufA*, were used to confirm their identities. This paper will thus elucidate the identity of important

commercial *Ulva* material and is the first study to place selected *Ulva* samples from Southern Africa into the recently developing consensus on *Ulva* molecular species identification.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection sites

Fresh *Ulva* specimens were collected from five abalone farms, Irvin & Johnson Cape Abalone, Abagold, Buffeljags Abalone, Diamond Coast Aquaculture, and Wild Coast Abalone. Fresh *Ulva* blades (a total of 12 specimens) were collected from land-based paddle-raceway systems, and attached *Ulva* specimens (four samples close to the farm inlet pipes—joint water intake of the farms—and 3 samples from near the outlets—outflow pipes of the farms) observed near the main abalone farming area in Hermanus were also collected. An additional 14 specimens were collected from nearby seashores (Kommetjie, Sea Point, Eersterivier, and Knysna) as well as foliose *Ulva* from Namibia (Swakopmund and Lüderitz), made available through the intertidal biodiversity survey conducted by the Benguela Current Commission (BCC) in 2019 (Figure 1; Table 1). Specimens were identified morphologically using the detailed descriptions in Stegenga et al. (1997). The size, texture, and color of the *Ulva* specimens were assessed visually, and the maximum length and width of the blades were measured. The anatomical characters recorded included the dentations on the blade margin, blade thickness, vegetative cell lengths and cell width, number of pyrenoids per cell, shape of cells in surface view, and the chloroplast arrangement in the cells (Bachoo, 2021). Photomicrographs were taken using an Olympus D50 digital camera mounted on the microscope, and a scale bar was included (Appendix S1 in the Supporting Information). All specimens were pressed and dried on herbarium sheets for deposit in the Bolus Herbarium at the University of Cape Town (BOL) or storage in the Seaweed Biorepository at the University of Cape Town. Fresh *Ulva* samples were stored in pre-labeled plastic bags and immediately stored in a -80°C freezer for DNA analysis. Additional sequences from three farms and nearby seashores (ITS rDNA region: 14 sequences; *rbcl*: 14 sequences) were added from a previous unpublished study (Table 1).

DNA extraction and PCR amplification

DNA was extracted from fresh or silica-dried *Ulva* samples using the QIAamp DNA Micro Kit (50; Cat# 56304) following the manufacturer's instructions with minor modifications that included the elution of DNA in $30\ \mu\text{L}$ of elution buffer and incubation with the elution buffer

FIGURE 1 Location of commercial abalone farms and seashore sites where *Ulva* samples were collected. The sequence of numbers for the collection sites are arranged in ascending order from west to east. The five main *Ulva*-producing commercial abalone farms along the coastline of South Africa are numbered 3 (Diamond Coast Aquaculture), 6 (Abagold Abalone), 7 (Irvin & Johnson Cape Abalone), 8 (Buffeljags Abalone) and 11 (Wild Coast Abalone). The seashore sites are numbered 1 (Swakopmund), 2 (Lüderitz), 4 (Sea Point), 5 (Kommetjie), 9 (Knysna) and 10 (Eersterivier).

for 5 min at room temperature before centrifugation. Samples were ground in liquid nitrogen, and ≤ 10 mg was used for DNA extraction. Prior to PCR amplification, the quantity and quality of the extracted DNA was estimated using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (GENOVA NANO, JENWAY, Bibby Scientific Ltd.), and the integrity of the extracted DNA was assessed on a 1% agarose gel to ensure the presence of high molecular weight DNA. Fragments of the *rbcL*, ITS rDNA region, and *tufA* gene regions were PCR amplified using a Bio-Rad C1000™ thermal cycler with the primers RH1 (5'-ATGTCACCACAAACAGAACTAAAGC-3') and 1385r (5'-AATTCAAATTTAATTTCTTTCC-3'; Manhart, 1994), primers ITS5 (5'-GGAAGTAAAGTCGTAACAAGG-3') and ITS4 (5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3'; White et al., 1990), and primers *tufGF4* (5'-GGNGCNGC NCAAATGGAYGG-3'; Saunders & Kucera, 2010) and *tufAR* (5'-CCTTCNCGAATMGCRAAWCGC-3'; Famà et al., 2002), respectively. All PCR reaction mixtures (25 μ L volume) were prepared using 2 μ L of approximately 50 ng \cdot μ L⁻¹ DNA extract, 1 \times (12.5 μ L) PCR-Master Mix (KAPA Taq ReadyMix, Kapa Biosystems; Catalog #KK1006), 0.5 μ L (400 nM) of each primer, and 9.5 μ L of sterile water. The PCR amplification thermal profile for each marker is listed in Table S1 in the Supporting Information. Polymerase chain reaction products were assessed on a 1% agarose gel to verify reaction specificity and fragment size, and PCR products were purified (Roche) and sequenced at the Central Analytical Unit at Stellenbosch University using a BigDye Terminator Cycle Sequencing Kit (Applied Biosystems) and AB13730xl Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems)

according to the manufacturer's instructions. Some PCR products were sent to MacroGen-Europe for sequencing and were purified by centrifugation using the Wizard® SV Gel and the PCR Clean-Up System prior to the sequencing reactions. Both forward and reverse primers for each gene were used for cycle sequencing.

Phylogenetic analyses

A total of 33 *rbcL* gene (1501 bp), 20 ITS rDNA region (1316 bp) and 33 *tufA* gene (1224 bp) sequences were obtained in the present study, and 14 *rbcL* gene and 14 ITS rDNA sequences were included from a previous unpublished study (L. Kandjengo, unpub. data). Additional *Ulva* sequences were selected from the nucleotide collection available in GenBank and relevant sequences from previous publications were added for comparison with Southern African material (Fort et al., 2021; Hughey et al., 2022; Kirkendale et al., 2013; Loughnane et al., 2008; Melton et al., 2016). This yielded multiple alignments with a total of 76 *rbcL* gene, 82 ITS rDNA region, 83 *tufA* gene sequences and a concatenated alignment of 60 *rbcL* and *tufA* gene sequences. All sequences were edited using the software BioEdit Sequence Alignment Editor version 7.0.5.3 (Hall, 1999). Phylogenetic analyses for the *rbcL* gene, ITS rDNA region, *tufA* gene sequences, and concatenated datasets were performed using the maximum likelihood (ML) analysis in RaxML via the online portal CIPRES (Miller et al., 2010) and Bayesian inference (BI) analysis in MrBayes v3.2 (Ronquist

TABLE 1 Collection and specimen details.

Species	Sample code	GenBank accession numbers			Collection site	Latitude; Longitude	Collector ^a	Date
		rbcL	ITS	tufA				
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	BL-S	OL778868	OM141569	OL778883	Buffeljags Abalone, Cape south coast, South Africa	34°45'16.4" S, 19°36'50.5" E	JJB & MMR	07 Jun 2018
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	BL-E	OL778860	OM141567	OL778894				
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	AG-P1	OL778859	OM141565	OL778893	Abagold Farm, Hermanus, South Africa	34°25'58.2" S, 19°13'14.4" E	JJB & MMR	18 Jun 2018
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	AG-M1	OL778867	OM141574	OL778892				
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	AG-M2	OL778869	OM141572	OL778882				
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	KS-Coiled	OL778865	OM141570	OL778890	Diamond Coast Aquaculture, South Africa	29°40'43.2" S, 17°03'29.3" E	JJB & MMR	13 Jun 2018
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	KS-Flat	OL778866	OM141571	OL778891				
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	HG-1	OL778861	OM141568	OL778885	Wild Coast Abalone, Haga-Haga, South Africa	32°45'01.7" S, 28°16'24.5" E	JJB & MMR	11 Jun 2018
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	HG-2	OL778862	OM141566	OL778886				
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	HG-3	OL778863	OM141564	OL778887				
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	HG-4	OL778871	OM141563	OL778888				
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	I&J	OL778864	OM141573	OL778889	Irvin & Johnson Cape Abalone, Danger Point, South Africa	34°37'44.1" S, 19°18'00.3" E	JJB & MMR	20 Jun 2018
<i>Ulva muscoides</i>	D2991-GT	OL778905	OM141562	OL778890	Kommetjie, South Africa	34°08'29.9" S, 18°19'23.0" E	JJB	18 Feb 2019
<i>Ulva compressa</i>	D2993-GT	OL778897		OL778891				
<i>Ulva uncialis</i>	D2994-GT	OL778911		OL778892	Kommetjie, South Africa	34°08'29.9" S, 18°19'23.0" E	JJB	08 Apr 2019
<i>Ulva compressa</i>	D2995-SAK	OL778898		OL778893				
<i>Ulva compressa</i>	D2996-MGK	OL778899		OL778894				
<i>Ulva compressa</i>	SPT-UC	OL778901		OL778895	Sea Point, South Africa	33°55'16.7" S, 18°22'41.6" E	JJB	19 May 2019
<i>Ulva compressa</i>	SPT-UL	OL778900		OL778896				
<i>Ulva australis</i>	SPT-UR	OL778920		OL778897				
<i>Ulva ohnoi</i>	D3044	OL778914	OM141561	OL778898	Eersterivier, South Africa	34°04'10.4" S, 24°12'43.7" E	MMR & DD	14 Jun 2019
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	D3047	OL778902	OL804296	OL778899	Knysna, South Africa	34°02'14.5" S, 23°01'02.9" E	MMR & DD	16 Jun 2019
<i>Ulva uncialis</i>	D3049	OL778909	OM146566	OL778900	Kommetjie	34°08'29.9" S, 18°19'23.0" E	JJB	15 Aug 2019
<i>Ulva australis</i>	NAM19	OL778923		OL778901	Swakopmund, Namibia	22°38'05.7" S, 14°31'34.1" E	MMR	11 Oct 2019
<i>Ulva australis</i>	NAM102	OL778924		OL778902	Lüderitz, Namibia	26°38'02.7" S, 15°09'43.8" E	MMR	11 Oct 2019
<i>Ulva uncialis</i>	NAM103	OL778913	OM146564	OL778903				
<i>Ulva uncialis</i>	AG-IN1	OL778910	OM146563	OL778904	Abagold Farm Complex, Hermanus (Inlets), South Africa	34°25'58.2" S, 19°13'14.4" E	JJB, BMM & MMR	30 Oct 2019
<i>Ulva australis</i>	AG-IN2	OL778921		OL778905				
<i>Ulva laciniolata</i>	AG-IN3	OL778858	OM141575	OL778906				
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	AG-IN4	OL778903		OL778907				

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Species	Sample code	GenBank accession numbers			Collection site	Latitude; Longitude	Collector ^a	Date
		<i>rbcL</i>	ITS	<i>tufA</i>				
<i>Ulva uncialis</i>	AG-OUT1	OL778912	OM146565	OL778908	Abagold Farm Complex, Hermanus (Outlets), South Africa	34°26'02.39" S, 19°13'33.59" E	JJB, BMM & MMR	30 Oct 2019
<i>Ulva australis</i>	AG-OUT3	OL778922		OL778909				
<i>Ulva aragoënsis</i>	AG-OUT4	OL778904		OL778910				
<i>Ulva uncialis</i>	U03	OL778906			Irvin & Johnson Cape Abalone, Danger Point, South Africa	34°37'44.1" S, 19°18'00.3" E	LK	2009
<i>Ulva lacunculata</i>	U114	OL778853						
<i>Ulva lacunculata</i>	U117	OL778854						

^aJJB, John J. Bolton; BMM, Brett M. Macey; MMR, Maggie M. Reddy; LK, Lineekela Kandjengo; DD, David Dyer.

& Huelsenbeck, 2003). For the Bayesian analysis, two concurrent Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) runs, each composed of four chains—three heated and one cold—were performed. Each Markov chain was run for 5,000,000 generations for the *rbcL* gene, ITS rDNA region, *tufA* gene, and concatenated datasets, sampling trees every 1000 generations. The first 25% of trees were discarded as burn-in. Parameter stability and run convergence were inspected using Tracer v1.7.1 (Rambaut et al., 2018). The consensus tree was generated from the remaining 75% of trees. For the maximum likelihood trees, the best evolutionary model for each of the three alignments was determined based on their Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) score calculated in jModeltest 2 (Darriba et al., 2012; Guindon & Gascuel, 2003). The TIM3, TIM1, and GTR+I+G were the most appropriate models for the *rbcL* gene, ITS rDNA region, *tufA* gene, and concatenated alignments, respectively. Maximum likelihood trees were obtained using RaxML-NG, and the trees were run for 100 bootstrap replicates (Kozlov et al., 2019). All trees were visualized using Figtree (<http://tree.bio.ed.ac.uk/>) and edited using Corel Draw.

RESULTS

Specimens of *Ulva* ($n=12$) collected from land-based paddle raceway systems from various integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa were morphologically identified as either *U. rigida* or *U. lactuca* (Bachoo, 2021). However, all specimens were resolved in a single DNA clade containing the type specimen of *U. lacunculata* with low support (posterior probabilities, PP: 0.60) for the *rbcL* gene (Figure S1 in the Supporting Information) but moderate support for *tufA* gene (Figure S2 in the Supporting Information), ITS rDNA region (Figure 2), and the concatenated dataset (ITS-PP: 0.92; *tufA*-PP: 0.97 & bootstrap percentage, BP: 92; Concat-PP: 0.92 & BP: 92; Figure 3). A single sample (AG-IN3), attached to farm infrastructure collected near the inlet pipes of the Hermanus farming complex, was morphologically identified as *U. rigida*, but resolved in the same clade. Specimens of *Ulva* ($n=16$) similarly collected from land-based paddle raceways from three farms, Irvin & Johnson Cape Abalone, Abagold, and Wild Coast Abalone in 2009 were morphologically identified as *U. rigida*, *U. capensis*, *U. linza*, and *U. lactuca*, but were all resolved within the larger *U. lacunculata* clade with low support (PP: 0.60) for the *rbcL* gene (Figure S1) and high support (PP: 0.92) for the ITS rDNA region (Figure 2).

In our concatenated phylogeny, *Ulva lacunculata* (PP: 0.97, BB: 92) and *U. sp. A* (PP: 1, BB: 100) were recovered in distinct sister clades (Figure 3). The latter clade contained specimens morphologically identified as *U. uncialis*. For all other genes, *U. uncialis* was recovered as an internal clade within the larger *U. lacunculata* with

FIGURE 2 Bayesian Inference tree for *Ulva* based on ITS rDNA region sequences (scale indicated at the bottom of the phylogeny). The topology was congruent with the ML tree. The tree was rooted with *Percursaria perscura*, *Umbraulva olivascens*, and *Ulvaria obscura*. Posterior probability values (PP) for the Bayesian analysis followed bootstrap values for the maximum likelihood (ML) analysis (≥ 70) and are indicated at each node. South African specimens are in gray. Numbers accompanying the species names are GenBank accession numbers for the sequences used in the analysis.

FIGURE 3 Bayesian Inference tree of *Ulva* species from the concatenated dataset, *tufA* and *rbcL* genes. The tree was rooted with *Ulvaria obscura*. Posterior probability values (PP) for the Bayesian analysis followed bootstrap values for the maximum likelihood (ML) analysis (≥ 70) and are indicated at each node. South African specimens are in gray. The asterisks (*) next to the five *Ulva* species indicate new *Ulva* records for Southern Africa.

moderate to high support (*rbcL*-PP: 0.7; *tufA*-PP: 1, BP: 97; ITS-PP: 0.75, BP: 70). Four farmed specimens (U03, U16, U21, U21F) collected in 2009 were also resolved in the internal *U. uncialis* clade for the ITS rDNA region (Figure 2) and *rbcL* gene (Figure S1), and three specimens (U09, U134 and U135) were identified as *U. stenophylloides* for the ITS rDNA region (Figure 1). However, no farmed material after 2009 contained specimens of *U. uncialis* or *U. stenophylloides*, although seashore material and specimens attached to farm infrastructure just outside the farms was consistent with *U. uncialis* (D3049 and AG-OUT1).

Specimens from nearby seashores or in close proximity to the aquaculture farms were morphologically identified as *Ulva rigida*, *U. capensis*, *U. lactuca*, *U. fasciata*, *U. uncialis*, and *U. flexuosa*, but all were resolved as different molecular species with high support (Figure 3). Similarly, specimens from nearby seashores collected in

2009 were morphologically identified as *U. rigida*, *U. capensis*, *U. uncialis*, and *U. lactuca* but were resolved as different molecular species with high support (Figure 3). One specimen (U03) collected on the seashore from Yzerfontein on the west coast of South Africa in 2009 resolved within the *U. lacinulata* DNA clade, which included the cultivated *Ulva* specimens. The molecular identification of seashore specimens included five new distribution records—*U. ohnoi*, *U. australis*, *U. stenophylloides*, *U. lacinulata*, and *U. aragoënsis*—and the first record of a foliose form of *U. compressa* for South Africa and one new distribution record for Namibia (*U. australis*).

DISCUSSION

Our results indicate that all currently cultivated *Ulva* in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in

South Africa are the same species, despite their wide geographical distribution and contrasting environmental conditions. All locally farmed *Ulva* specimens were identified as *U. lacinulata* following the recent nomenclatural change by Hughey et al. (2022). *Ulva lacinulata* is the oldest and therefore the valid taxonomic name for the molecular clade previously identified as *U. laetevirens* sensu Fort et al. (2021) that contained the type specimens of various species including *U. armoricana*. *Ulva armoricana* is a name that has been used for *Ulva* cultivated in South Africa (Cyrus et al., 2015). *Ulva laetevirens* was recently synonymized with *U. australis* by Hughey et al. (2021), and the lectotype specimen of *U. lacinulata* was resolved within the clade containing *U. laetevirens* sensu Fort et al. (2021) by Hughey et al. (2022), which means that the new valid name for this clade is *U. lacinulata*.

In their attempt to match names to DNA clades, Hughey et al. (2022) recognized a single, well-supported *rbcL* clade, to which they assigned the name *Ulva lacinulata*. This clade, however, contained sequences that were recovered in two separate clades according to Fort et al. (2021). *Ulva lacinulata* and *Ulva* sp. A, a closely related and undescribed species, were recovered as distinct clades based on a comprehensive collection of *tufA* gene, ITS1 rDNA region, and *rbcL* gene sequences to which different species DNA delimitation methods were applied (Fort et al., 2021). At the time, *Ulva* sp. A contained specimens misidentified as *U. rigida* or *U. lactuca*, but there were no available species names that could be unambiguously assigned to it. In the present study, specimens consistent with the morphology of *U. uncialis* (previously *U. capensis*) were firmly placed within the *Ulva* sp. A clade for all individual gene phylogenies and for the well-supported concatenated phylogeny. We therefore propose using the name *U. uncialis* for the clade previously referred to as *Ulva* sp. A by Fort et al. (2021). However, future studies and sequencing of the type specimen of *Phycoseris uncialis*, the basionym of the species, is still needed to confirm our assignment of the clade.

Molecular support for the *Ulva lacinulata* and *U. uncialis* clades was generally higher for the concatenated phylogeny and for the fast evolving ITS rDNA region and the *tufA* gene, but lacked resolution for the *rbcL* gene which might explain the lack of distinction within the *U. lacinulata rbcL* clade by Hughey et al. (2022). Other studies have similarly found that *tufA* is the most suitable molecular marker for species-level identification of *Ulva* species compared with the other commonly used markers, *rbcL* gene and ITS rDNA region. Although it has better amplification success and higher resolution compared with the other markers, the *tufA* gene is limited by a lack of available reference sequences for comparison, which makes linking Linnaean names to species clades particularly difficult (Tran et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the lack of a reference library for the *tufA*

gene should not limit its use in future studies. Our combined phylogenetic analysis of *tufA* and *rbcL* genes shows even better resolution than any single gene tree and is therefore recommended for future studies of this nature. Despite the low *rbcL* divergence between *U. lacinulata* and *U. uncialis*, we believe that these two entities should be tentatively considered different species as South African specimens are easily distinguished based on morphological characters. *Ulva lacinulata* has a thick, dark thallus, smooth margin and rectangular cells, and *U. uncialis* has a lighter, thinner thallus, teeth along the thallus margin and bullet shaped cells (see the description of *Ulva capensis* in Stegenga et al., 1997). However, further studies documenting the range of morphological variation in each of these clades are urgently needed. If *U. uncialis* is considered a distinct species, then the distribution of the species, previously known from South Africa and Namibia, would include Ireland, Scotland, France, Spain, Portugal, the United States, Chile, and New Zealand based on DNA records (as *Ulva* sp. A, sensu Fort et al., 2021).

At least four specimens of *Ulva uncialis* and three specimens of *U. stenophylloides* have been collected from the land-based paddle raceways in the past (I&J in 2009), but none were present in any of the new collections, which suggests that *U. lacinulata* has likely been selected over these species under culture conditions. Alternatively, it could indicate that these species occur in low abundance or sporadically in integrated aquaculture systems. Nevertheless, it does suggest different physiological and growth potential (Fort et al., 2019) in at least two entities (*U. lacinulata* and *U. uncialis*) and further supports our decision to retain them as distinct species.

The persistence of *Ulva lacinulata* in culture for such a long period of time is probably due to its effective vegetative growth and its ability to withstand a range of environmental conditions, such as the contrasting temperature regimes experienced in the various sampled farms. This wide tolerance in environmental conditions is not surprising given the relatively wide distribution range of this species. At least one specimen of *U. lacinulata* was observed growing attached near the inlet area of the main farming complex in Hermanus, and another specimen (LK14) was observed on the seashore in Yzerfontein (west coast) in South Africa in 2009. *Ulva* taxonomy has been in constant flux with the application of DNA; therefore, any suggestion of introduced species in South Africa is purely speculative. It is possible that *U. lacinulata* might have always been present on the seashore in South Africa but was mistakenly identified as *U. rigida* and *U. lactuca* based on overlapping morphological characters with these species and the lack of DNA confirmation. Indeed, *U. lacinulata* was previously considered *U. rigida* until the type specimens of both species were sequenced (see Hughey et al., 2022). The clade also contained specimens assigned to *U. lacinulata* ssp.

lactuca. It is therefore not surprising that *U. lacinulata* would have been previously misidentified as *U. rigida* or *U. lactuca* based on morphology. More importantly, this reiterates the need for DNA confirmation of commercially important species (Reddy et al., 2018, 2020, 2023), as different species may perform better than others in culture (Fort et al., 2019). More recently, the identification of *Ulva* specimens commercially cultivated in Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) in Portugal was carried out (Califano et al., 2020). These specimens were identified as *U. rigida* (MN444712, MN450419, and MN450422), but were recovered in the same clade as the cultivated *Ulva* specimens from South Africa. This indicates that both South Africa and Portugal are independently cultivating *U. lacinulata*, unattached in land-based IMTA systems, in South Africa with abalone and in Portugal with fish. A recent study, however, used *U. ohnoi* in their experimental IMTA system using seaweed, shrimp, and fish (de Moraes et al., 2023).

A comparison of *Ulva* specimens collected from nearby seashores unexpectedly resulted in several new *Ulva* records (DNA confirmed) along the seashores of South Africa and Namibia. These included *U. lacinulata*, *U. ohnoi*, *U. australis*, *U. stenophylloides*, and *U. aragoënsis*. All these specimens may have been encountered in the past but were likely mistakenly identified. According to the existing morphological classification of *Ulva* species in Southern Africa, *U. lacinulata* was morphologically identified as either *U. rigida* or *U. lactuca* sensu Stegenga et al. (1997); *U. ohnoi* as *U. uncialis* sensu Joska (1992); *U. australis* as either *U. rigida* sensu Stegenga et al. (1997) or *U. lactuca* sensu Stegenga et al. (1997); and *U. aragoënsis* as *U. flexuosa* sensu Stegenga et al. (1997). Furthermore, a foliose form of *Ulva compressa* (Steinhagen, Weinberger, & Karez, 2019) was also found and has not been previously documented on the seashores of South Africa. However, Stegenga et al. (1997) has a drawing and description (as *Enteromorpha compressa*) of the tubular form of the species.

The new *Ulva* records in Southern Africa extend the distribution ranges for several species, some of which were thought to have a much more restricted range. *Ulva ohnoi* was described from Japan in 2004 (type from Tosa Bay, Tosa, Kochi Prefecture; Hirakawa et al., 2004). *Ulva ohnoi* occurs in warm temperate waters, and the single South African specimen (D3044), from Eersterivier (south coast of South Africa), is consistent with this finding. Since its description, the species has been widely recorded around the world (Guiry & Guiry, 2023), but this is the first record from sub-Saharan Africa. *Ulva australis* was originally reported from Port Adelaide, South Australia and later included *U. pertusa*, *U. laetevirens*, and *U. spathulata* as synonyms. Due to the morphological resemblance between *U. rigida* and *U. australis* these two species were at one-time synonymized

but were later shown to be genetically distinct (Kraft et al., 2010). The species is widely distributed and is now recorded from South Africa. *Ulva stenophylloides* was described from Victoria, Australia, in 2010. It was only known from Australia and New Zealand, but now also from South Africa. *Ulva aragoënsis* was also molecularly identified among our seashore *Ulva* specimens. The name *U. aragoënsis* was assigned to a clade containing specimens previously assigned to *U. mediterranea*, a replacement name for *Enteromorpha aragoënsis* Bliding (Alongi et al., 2014). The name *U. mediterranea* was however considered a superfluous name (Krupnik et al., 2018) and was subsumed into *U. aragoënsis*. Lastly, a foliose form of *U. compressa* is reported from South Africa for the first time. Studies have shown that *U. mutabilis*, which was synonymized with *U. compressa*, has a range of morphologies such as tubular, bladed and a mixed morphotype (Steinhagen, Barco, et al., 2019; Steinhagen, Weinberger, & Karez, 2019).

Our study focused on resolving the identity of commercially cultivated species of *Ulva* in South Africa and unexpectedly resulted in the identification of several new records and assigning a Linnean name to an unnamed clade. The most obvious next step would be to carry out a comprehensive survey of *Ulva* species from Southern Africa.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Teejaswani Bachoo: Data curation (equal); formal analysis (equal); investigation (equal); methodology (equal); writing – original draft (equal). **John J. Bolton:** Conceptualization (equal); funding acquisition (equal); investigation (equal); project administration (equal); resources (equal); supervision (equal); validation (equal); writing – review and editing (equal). **Brett M. Macey:** Conceptualization (equal); methodology (equal); resources (equal); supervision (equal); writing – review and editing (equal). **Lineekela Kandjengo:** Investigation (equal); resources (equal); writing – review and editing (equal). **Maggie M. Reddy:** Conceptualization (equal); data curation (equal); formal analysis (equal); investigation (equal); methodology (equal); project administration (equal); supervision (equal); validation (equal); writing – original draft (equal); writing – review and editing (equal).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Appendix S1. Photomicrographs of cultivated specimens including a scale bar.

Table S1. PCR thermocycling conditions for each gene region.

Figure S1. Bayesian Inference tree for *Ulva* based on *rbcL* gene sequences (scale at the bottom of the phylogeny). The BI topology was congruent with the ML tree. The tree was rooted with *Blidingia minima* and *Monostroma nitidum*. Posterior probability values (PP) for the Bayesian analysis followed bootstrap values for the maximum likelihood (ML) analysis (≥ 70) and are indicated at each node. Numbers accompanying the species names are GenBank accession numbers for the sequences used in the analysis.

Figure S2. Bayesian Inference tree for *Ulva* based on *tufA* gene sequences (scale at the bottom of the phylogeny). The BI topology was congruent with the ML tree. The tree was rooted with *Ulvaria obscura*. Posterior probability values (PP) for the Bayesian analysis followed bootstrap values for the maximum likelihood (ML) analysis (≥ 70) and are indicated at each node. Numbers accompanying the species names are GenBank accession numbers for the sequences used in the analysis.

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